

EFFICACY OF SAPTAMRITA LAUHA IN MANAGEMENT OF PARINAM SHOOLA W.S.R. DUODENAL ULCER

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Parinama Shoola is an Avaranjanya Tridoshaj Vyadhi predominantly involving Vata and Pitta, characterized by epigastric pain occurring during the digestion phase (3–4 hours post-meal). It shows clinical resemblance to duodenal ulcer in contemporary medicine. Saptamrita Lauha, a classical Herbo-mineral formulation containing Yashtimadhu, Triphala, and Lauha Bhasma, possesses Pittashamak, Shoolaprasamana, and Vranaropan properties. **Aim:** To evaluate the clinical efficacy of Saptamrita Lauha in the management of Parinama Shoola. **Materials and Methods:** An open-label, single-arm clinical study was conducted on 20 patients diagnosed with Parinama Shoola. Saptamrita Lauha was administered at a dose of 250 mg twice daily with appropriate Anupana for 30 days. Assessment was based on subjective parameters including epigastric pain, tenderness, heartburn, nausea, and other

associated symptoms. Statistical analysis was performed using paired t-test with significance set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** Statistically significant improvement ($p < 0.05$) was observed in most clinical parameters including epigastric pain, tenderness, heartburn, and eructation. Most patients (70%) showed marked improvement ($>75%$), while 20% showed moderate improvement and 10% showed mild improvement. However, improvement in nausea (Hrillasa) was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). No adverse effects were reported during

the study period. **Conclusion:** Saptamrita Lauha demonstrated significant clinical improvement in the symptoms of Parinama Shoola in this preliminary study. However, larger randomized controlled trials with objective diagnostic parameters are required to establish definitive efficacy.

KEYWORDS: Parinama Shoola, Saptamrita Lauha, Duodenal Ulcer, Ayurveda, Vranaropan, Pittashamak.

INTRODUCTION

The digestive system is one of the biological systems that has been negatively affected by the fast paced, stressful, and busy modern world (Annavaha Srotas). The term "Annavaha Srotas" refers to the path taken by food during transportation.^[1] The Annavaha Srotas (alimentary canal) takes part in the following processes: Anna Adana (food intake), Anna Pachana (digestion), Sara Kitta Virechana (separation of nutrient and waste part), and Rasa Shoshana (nutrient absorption). According to Ayurveda, Dehagni is in charge of life, appearance, strength, health, Oja, Teja, and Prana. Ama occurs from any discord at any level of the Annavaha Srotas or the Dehagni. jeerna, Ama-Visha creation, Anna Drava Shoola and Parinama Shoola are the next stages of the digestive process that are triggered by an intermediate product that is produced as a result of the digestive fire's disturbed metabolism. According to research, peptic and duodenal ulcers are associated with Anna Drava and Parinama Shoola, respectively. The phrase "Parinama Shoola" refers to abdominal colic, also known as Shoola, which occurs during food digestion, or about three to four hours after ingestion, after food has entered the intestines.^[2]

The Acharya Madhav Nidana referred to Parinama Shoola as an "Avarana Janya, Tridoshaj Vyadhi" and Anna Drava Shoola as a sort of Shoola with the distinguishing characteristics of discomfort before and throughout food digestion and that relieves after vomiting.^[3] The cause of Anna Drava Shoola is explained as Vata Prakopa, in which the aggrieved Vata dosha surrounds nearby Pitta and Kapha doshas in the Koshtha and becomes potent enough to produce colic pain during the digestion of ingested food. Kapha breaks down from its own location and interacts with Pitta and Vata to cause colic pain during the transformation of the food consumed. Duodenal Ulcer) is characterized by burning sensation in the epigastric area that is worsened by fasting and relieved by eating.^[4] An ulcer is defined as a local defect brought on by active inflammation that compromises the mucosal integrity of the stomach or duodenal wall. Usually chronic in nature, ulcers develop in the stomach or duodenum. 4

million people (new cases and recurrences) in the United States are affected with duodenal and acid peptic illnesses each year, making them quite prevalent. In the United States, ulcer affects 10% of women and 12% of men during their lifetimes.^[5]

These prevalent illnesses have had a significant budgetary impact, with an estimated burden on direct and indirect health care expenses of \$10 billion annually in the United States. Anna Drava Shoola and Parinama Shoola have been linked to ulcer illness in current research and clinically correlated with duodenal ulcer.^[6] Numerous people suffer from duodenal ulcers, which are the most prevalent gastrointestinal illnesses in clinical settings. It is widely acknowledged that abnormalities in the mucosal protective factors are what lead to ulcers.^[7]

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The clinical study is to evaluate the efficacy of Saptamrita Lauha in the management of Parinama Shoola. In the present study the diagnosed cases of Parinama Shoola were randomly selected and subjected to clinical trial. The method of clinical trial & observations is as follows.

Source of Data

(OPD number 1 Kayachikitsa OPD of Pt shivshakti college of ayurved, Ratlam)

Criteria for selection of patients

Patients with classical signs & symptoms of Parinama Shoola will be randomly selected for the study, irrespective of age, sex, religion, occupation etc.

Sample size; Single trial group of 20 patients was taken for the study to evaluate the efficacy of the trial drug.

Inclusion Criteria

- Age 15-70 years.
- Patients with classical sign & symptoms of Parinama shool (Duodenal Ulcer)

Exclusion Criteria

- Age > 70 years
- Recurrent episodes of severe pain restricting the patients from daily routine work.
- Associated complication (Hourglass stomach or pyloric stenosis)
- Immuno-compromised patients (i.e., HIV, Tuberculosis etc.)

- Other complicated disorders (i.e., Zollinger-Ellison syndrome, liver cirrhosis etc.)

Informed consent

- An informed written consent was obtained from all included subjects.

Investigation

- Blood Examination: Hb%.
- Stool examination: For ova, cyst, pus, occult blood etc.

Drug

In this study we had use trial drug, which is Saptamrita Lauha having Lauha Bhasma with Yashtimadhu, Haritaki, Bibhitaki and Amalaki. Largest ingredients of Saptamrita Lauha have Deepan, Pachan, Pittashamak, Shoolanashak, Vatanulomak, Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Anti-spasmodic, properties, which may be helpful to cure the cardinal symptoms of Parinama Shoola.

Dose-250 mg twice daily with honey as Anupana like milk or ghee.

Duration: Total duration of the treatment was 30 days.

Follow up - 56 days and 70 days.

CRITERIA OF ASSESSMENT

Subjective Criteria

1. Epigastric pain during digestion of food (bhukte jeeryati yat shulam)

0 – No pain

1 – Occasional mild pain

2 – Moderate pain during digestion of every meal

3 – Severe pain during digestion of every meal

2. Epigastric tenderness

0 – No pain

1 – Mild tenderness sometimes

2 – Persistent moderate tenderness

3 – Persistent severe tenderness

3. Hunger pain

- 0 – No pain
- 1 – Occasional mild pain
- 2 – Moderate pain during hunger after every meal
- 3 – Severe pain during hunger after every meal.
- 4. Malabaddhata (Constipation)

- 0 – Normal bowels
- 1 – Hard bowels once/ twice a day
- 2 – Hard bowels once in two days
- 3 – Severe pain during hunger after every meal
- 5. Adhmana (distension of abdomen)

- 0 – No distention
- 1 – Sometimes mild distention
- 2 – Moderate persistent distention
- 3 – Severe persistent distention
- 6. Hritkanta daha (heart burn)

- 0 – No heart burn
- 1 – Mild occasional heart burn
- 2 – Moderate heart burn & throat burning
- 3 – Severe heart burn & throat burning
- 7. Tikta amla Udgara (Sour & bitter eructation)

- 0 – No eructation
- 1 – Mild eructation sometimes
- 2 – Moderate eructation even on sitting
- 3 – Severe persistent eructation
- 8. Hrilasa (nausea)

- 0 – No nausea
- 1 – Mild nausea occasionally
- 2 – persistent moderate nausea
- 3 – Persistent severe nausea
- 9. Chardii (vomiting)

0 – No vomiting

1 – 2 to 3 times vomiting / day

2 – 4 to 5 times moderate vomiting / day

3 – 5 or more than 5 times vomiting / day

DATA COLLECTION AND RESULT ANALYSIS

All twenty enrolled volunteers were directed to take Saptamrita Lauha orally for 30 days. The records become amassed in the form of diverse charts, graphs & tables. The records obtained were statistically analyzed by the Unpaired 't' test and fisher test and implemented for qualitative records to assess homogeneity. The level of importance was kept at $p=0.05$.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Because the threshold of significance for each part is equal to 0.05, there is strong evidence which marks that Saptamrita Lauha is effective in the management of Parinama shool significant improvement in most parameters except Hrilas. For all of the aforementioned factors, there is a significant variation in grades. The average rank values show that, for all criterions, grades are significantly falling as treatment days rise.

Clinical features	B.T. M+ S. D	A. T. M+ S.D.	S.E.	Mean Difference	T value	P value
Epigastric pain during digestion	2.25 + 0.44	0.00+ 0.00	0.099	2.25	22.650	<0.0001
Epigastric tenderness	1.75 + 0.72	0.10 + 0.31	0.131	1.65	12.567	<0.0001
Hunger pain	1.55+0.83	0.05 + 0.22	0.199	1.50	7.5498	<0.0001
<i>Malabaddhata</i>	1.05 + 0.60	0.05 + 0.22	0.145	1.50	7.5498	<0.0001
<i>Adhmana</i>	0.95 + 0.51	0.20 + 0.41	0.143	0.75	5. 2517	<0.0001
<i>Hritkanta - daha</i>	1.95+0.83	0.40 +0.50	0.153	1.55	10.099	<0.0001
Tiktaaamla udgara	1.40 +0.99	0.15 +0.37	0.190	1.25	6.5713	<0.0001
Hrilasa	0.50 +0.61	0.25 + 0.55	0.143	0.25	1.7506	<0.0961
Chardi	0.20 + 0.41	0.00+0.00	0.092	0.20	2.1794	<0.0421

OBSERVATION

1. Psychological Factors (Stress): Mental stress was identified as a primary factor in the development of the condition.
2. Genetic Predisposition (Heredity): A minority of the group showed a hereditary link.
3. Dietary Habits: A massive part of the patients often consume stimulants like tea and coffee.

4. Lifestyle Habits (Alcohol): Alcohol consumption was noted in a small segment of the group.
5. Physical Constitution (Deha Prakriti): The vast majority of patients showed a Vata-Pittaja constitution.
6. Mental Temperament (Manasa Prakriti): A high prevalence of Rajasika nature was seen among the individuals.
7. Disease Chronicity: More patients presented with chronic features than acute symptoms.
8. Dosha Predominance: The Vataja type was the most common manifestation, followed by Pittaja, with the Kaphaja type being the least frequent.

DISCUSSION

Saptamrita Lauha is a classical Ayurvedic Herbo-mineral formulation that proves highly effective in managing Parinama Shoola by balancing the vitiated Vata and Pitta doshas. According to Ayurvedic principles, Parinama Shoola is a Tridoshaj condition where pain typically occurs during the digestion of food.^[8] The formulation's key ingredients- Yashtimadhu (Licorice), Triphala (Amalaki, Haritaki, and Bibhitaki), and Lauha Bhasma (Iron calx)-work synergistically to pacify the hyperactive Pitta responsible for acidity and the Vata responsible for colicky pain.^[9] By neutralizing excessive acid (Amlata) and providing a soothing effect on the gastrointestinal mucosa, Saptamrita Lauha effectively alleviates the burning sensations and epigastric distress characteristic of duodenal ulcers.^[10]

The therapeutic efficacy of this medicine is further enhanced by its potent Vranaropan (ulcer-healing) and Shothahara (anti-inflammatory) properties.^[11] Yashtimadhu acts as a natural demulcent, creating a protective coating over the duodenal lining, while the antioxidant-rich Triphala supports tissue regeneration and keeps the mucosal barrier. Furthermore, the fine processing of Lauha Bhasma ensures high bioavailability, aiding in the correction of underlying Dhatu imbalances often associated with chronic digestive disorders.^[12] When administered with traditional adjuvants like honey and ghee, which function as Yogavāhi (catalysts), the formulation penetrates deeper into the tissues to promote systemic healing.

Beyond symptomatic relief, Saptamrita Lauha addresses the root causes of Parinama Shoola by improving Agni (digestive fire) and promoting proper Vatanulomana (downward movement of Vata).^[13] By easing better nutrient absorption and preventing the formation of Ama (metabolic toxins), it reduces the recurrence of bloating, flatulence, and abdominal distension. Its unique ability to function as a Rasayana (rejuvenative) ensures that while the

ulcer is treated, the overall strength and immunity of the digestive tract are bolstered.^[14] Consequently, Saptamrita Lauha serves as a comprehensive, safe, and cost-effective intervention for patients suffering from the chronic and often painful features of duodenal ulcers.

Overall effect of the therapy

The recorded data it is shows that good changes (>75%) in 14 cases and moderate changes (50%- 74.9%) in 4 cases, mild changes (25%–49.9%) in 2 cases, no changes (<25%) in 0 cases, for the complete subsidence of pain.

Mode of action

Saptamrita Lauha manages Parinama Shool (duodenal ulcers) by balancing aggravated Pitta and Vata doshas in the digestive tract. During digestion (Parinama), the formulation acts as a potent Shoolaprasamana (pain reliever) by soothing the gastric mucosa and neutralizing excess acid.^[15] Its Agni Deepana (digestive stimulant) properties ensure that food is processed correctly, preventing the formation of Ama (undigested toxins) that leads to the sharp, colicky pain characteristic of this condition.^[16] The combination of Lauha Bhasma and Yashtimadhu (Licorice) provides a dual healing effect: Lauha Bhasma aids in tissue regeneration and blood purification, while Yashtimadhu acts as a natural antacid and anti-inflammatory to protect the stomach lining. Additionally, the Triphala part ensures smooth bowel movements and clears channel obstructions (Srotoshodhana), addressing the root Vata imbalance that causes the abdominal distress.^[17]

CONCLUSION

The Ayurvedic management of Parinama shool has compelling evidence to break down the pathogenesis of this disease. The recovery in the present study was promising and worth documenting. In this study, it confirms that the Saptamrita Lauha showed significant clinical improvement in symptoms of Parinama Shoola in this small-scale study. Larger controlled trials are recommended.

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